

Effect of Mastery-Learning Approach on Academic Performance in Mole Concept among Secondary School Chemistry Students In Gombe Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigated effect of mastery learning approach on academic performance in mole concept among secondary school students in Gombe metropolis. The study employed quasi-experimental research design using pretest posttest non-randomized control group design. The population of the study consist of all Government Senior Secondary School class II Chemistry Students (2020/2021)1 academic session in Gombe metropolis, Gombe State. Simple random sampling technique by balloting technique was used to select 2 Schools in Gombe metropolis, Gombe State. A sample size of 85 (46 Male; 39 Female) class (II) students were selected for the study using an intact class. Two groups formed are Experimental Group and the Control Group. The instrument used Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) was validated and had a reliability coefficient of 0.78 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Two research questions guided the study with a corresponding hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test Inferential statistic. The finding revealed that there is significance difference in the academic performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method. Therefore, students in experimental group taught using mastery learning approach performed better than those in control group taught using lecture method. Based on findings, it was recommended among others that seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized by Educational Organizations such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) for chemistry teachers to update them with the use of Mastery Learning Approach so as to improve the academic performance of students.

Keywords: Chemistry, Mole Concept, Mastery-learning, and Academic Performance

Introduction

Chemistry Education plays a vital role towards the advancement of science and technology of a nation. This was explained by Emendu (2014) that Chemistry Education is one of the major bedrocks for the transformation of our national economy and further buttressed that there is a positive relationship between chemistry education and chemical industry. By implication, the higher the quality of chemistry education, the more the number of chemical industries produced by a country and the better the economy of the country. Chemistry is an essential science subject and is one of the core science subjects in the Senior Secondary Schools (SSS) curriculum in Nigeria. Thus, Mole concept is an aspect of chemistry that involves mathematical skills in solving problems. Mole Concept has been identified in teachers' guide for new senior secondary school chemistry curriculum as a difficult Concept in Chemistry. As a result of its difficulty to comprehend. This was confirmed by Bamidele, Adetunji, Awodele and Irinoye (2013) who explained that chemistry students are deficient in the use of the Mole Concept and its applications. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiner's Report (2018-2022) recorded poor performance in chemistry which was attributed to use of inappropriate teaching methods by teachers and poor mathematical skills by students in some concepts of chemistry. In Gombe State, where this study was carried out, the situation is not very

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different. The analysis showed that students have problem with chemistry subject at the SSSCE and poor passing grades fluctuate within the years under consideration. Lack of adequate and frequent use of activity based instructional strategies have been identified as the major cause of poor performance in chemistry (Adeyemo & Babajide, 2014).

Mastery Learning is an approach which involves breaking down the topic to be learned into units for easy assimilation by students. It is a method that frequently monitors the students' progress through formative assessment in each unit of a lesson with the view of providing feedback and reinforcement. Adeyemo & Babajide, (2014) described mastery learning as a teaching strategy that involves a pre-specified criterion level of performance which students must master in order to complete the instruction and move on. Furo (2017) maintained that Mastery Learning is a model where students are expected to master a learning objective or goal, before the students can move on to the next goal. For example, in a class room situation where a teacher is to teach the concept Amount, the stated objective for the first unit will be (i) to define Amount (ii) give the unit for Amount and (iii) give the formula for calculating Amount, the students can only proceed to the next unit (solving problems on Amount) after formative assessment was given based on the stated objective and the student achieved 80% mastery. If on the other hand, the students did not achieve 80% mastery, an additional study time will be given for corrections which will enable the student to improve in the mastery in order to proceed to the next unit. This shows that in a mastery learning model, all students have equal chance to reach the mastery level only if given unlimited learning period. This shows that in a mastery learning model, all students have equal chance to reach the mastery level only if given unlimited learning period. Also supported by Mitee and Obaitan (2015) that Philosophy of mastery learning assert that virtually all students are capable of attaining a high degree of learning if given the needed time and appropriate learning conditions and that if teachers could provide these appropriate conditions, virtually all students could reach a high level of performance and the differences in their level of performance would vanish. Mastery Learning Strategy (MLS) can help the teacher to identify students' area of weakness and correct it thus breaking the cycle of failure. Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) can help the teacher to identify students' area of weakness and correct it thus breaking the cycle of failure. On the basis of this background, the study intends to investigate the effect of mastery-learning approach on academic performance among senior secondary school chemistry students in Gombe metropolis.

Poor performance in science subjects among senior secondary schools have been of concern to educationists and researchers. In Nigeria and other developing countries, stakeholders in science education are interested in finding out the cause of the incessant poor performance in chemistry among secondary schools. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiner's Report (2014-2018) recorded poor performance in chemistry which was attributed to use of inappropriate teaching methods by teachers and poor mathematical skills by students in some concepts of chemistry. This poor performance increased to 69% between 2018 and 2021. Studies such as Meheux (2017), Filgona (2017), Sor, Jamabo and Igwe (2017) have shown that several factors are responsible for this poor performance, common among all is the teacher, teaching aid and his teaching methods. So also, Bamidele, *et al.* (2013) identified mole concept and its application to Stoichiometry as a difficult topic perceived by chemistry students in secondary school. Therefore, the researcher intends to teach mole concept using mastery learning approach in order to improve the academic performance of chemistry students.

Objectives of the Study

This study has the following objectives which are to:

1. Determine the effects of mastery learning approach on chemistry students' academic performance in mole concept.
2. Determine differences in academic performance between male and female students when taught using mastery learning approach.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions which are as follows:

1. What is the difference in academic performance mean scores among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture method?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method.

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2. There is no significant difference between the academic performance mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach.

Methodology

This study adopted pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental-control group design. The population for this study consist of all SSII 2018/19 session government secondary school chemistry students in Gombe metropolis. For the purpose of selecting the schools, Simple random sampling technique using ‘balloting method was used to select two (2) senior secondary schools out of eighteen Senior Secondary Schools in the population. This was achieved by writing the names of each secondary school on pieces of paper, fold and pour them inside a container. One of the students was asked to hand-pick 2 papers and drops each paper on two different containers labeled EG and CG. The two schools selected forms the subjects of the study, that is, the Experimental and Control Groups, consisting of both male and female students. This method ensured that each member of the population had equal and independent chance of being selected. A sample size of 85 (46 male; 39 female) SSII chemistry students were sampled using an intact class, which is in line with the central limit theorem. Pretest was administered to all the groups before the treatment to determine the groups’ equivalence based on the ability of the students. The Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) designed by the researcher was used to measure students’ academic performance, it consists of 50 multiple choice questions with four options constructed to serve as pretest to ascertain equivalence of ability of subjects and as posttest to determine the effects of the treatments on ability to solve numerical problems in chemistry based on the Mole Concept. The items consist of 33 calculations and 17 theories on mole concept. The instrument MCPT was developed from past question papers of external examination bodies such as West Africa Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) (1999-2019) and also practical chemistry textbook by Ojokuku. Each question was awarded 1 mark. The MCPT was validated by four lecturers and two experienced chemistry teachers in the secondary school who are seasoned examiners of WAEC and NECO, all corrections, suggestions and recommendation were noted. The reliability of the Mole Concept Performance Test (MCPT) was determined using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Formula, From the result obtained, r was calculated and found to be 0.78, indicating a strong positive relationship. Thus, the instrument MCPT is reliable to measure the academic performance of the study subjects. The Experimental Group students were taught mole concept using mastery learning approach while the control group students were taught the same concept using the lecture method. A posttest was administered to the two groups after six weeks of administering the pretest in order to determine the effectiveness of the treatments on the students. Data collected were statistically analysed. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS version 23.

Results

Research Question One

What is the difference in academic performance mean score among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture method?

Table.1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Academic Performance Scores Taught Using Mastery Learning Approach and Those Taught Using Lecture Methods

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	42	44.43	12.351	9.13
Control	43	35.30	6.964	

From Table 1, it can be seen that the mean score of experimental group is higher than the control group with a mean difference of 9.13. Therefore, there is a difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and those taught using lecture methods. This means that mastery learning approach enhances students’ academic performance in chemistry. However, to find out how significant the difference is, t-test was used in analyzing the scores.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean score among chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method.

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Table 2: Posttest t-test of Students' Performance Between Experimental Group and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. error mean	Df	p-value	Decision
Experimental	42	44.94	12.351	2.826	83	0.001	S
Control	43	35.30	6.964	2.261			

* Significant at $P < 0.05$ level

Table 2 shows that the p - value observed was 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 83 and 0.05 level of significance. The p - value of 0.001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 which is an indication that there is significant difference in the performance of students taught chemistry using mastery learning approach and that taught using lecture method. Based on the result of Table 2, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method is therefore rejected. There is significant difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach and that taught using lecture method.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean scores academic performance between male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach?

Table 3: Posttest Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Performance According to Gender in the Experimental Group

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference
Experimental Group	Male	37	44.41	10.303	0.04
	Female	32	44.45	14.555	

From Table 3, it can be seen that the mean scores of both male and female students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach in the experimental group is (44.41 and 44.45) respectively. Considering values obtained by both genders in the group, there is a difference in the performance of students taught using mastery learning approach based on gender. However, to find out how significant the difference is based on gender, student t test was used in analyzing the scores.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach and lecture method

Table 4.4: Posttest t-test of Students' Performance Between Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. error mean	Df	p-value	Decision
Male	22	44.41	10.303	2.801	40	0.001	S
Female	20	44.45	14.555	2.810			

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$ level

Table 4 shows that the p- value observed was 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 5 and 0.05 level of significance. The p- value of 0.001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 which is an indication that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach. Based on the result of Table 4, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach is therefore rejected. There is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female chemistry students taught using mastery learning approach.

Discussion of Findings

The objectives of this study were to investigate the effects of concept mapping strategy and mastery learning approach on reflective thinking and academic performance in mole concept among secondary school students' in Gombe state, Nigeria. The results are discussed as follows: The results from the research question on Table 1 and testing of hypothesis one on Table 2 indicated that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach and lecture method. The result also revealed that there is a significant difference between use of mastery learning and lecture method.

The significant difference in performance is in favour of the students in the Experimental Group taught using mastery learning approach. This is in line with the findings of Filgona (2017), Mayanchi, Anya and Kainuwa (2018). The finding from this study indicated that mastery learning approach can enhance academic performance among students and yield better result than Lecture method. Students in the experimental group taught using mastery learning might have learnt meaningfully because of the sequential evaluation of students' progress in every unit of the lesson which is absent in the control group, students in the control group taught using lecture method are mere passive listener.

Results from the research question and testing of hypothesis two from Table 3 showed that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female when exposed to mastery learning approach. This means that mastery-learning approach is an instructional strategy that is gender friendly as it gives equality in learning for both sexes. This result is equally in line with the result of Wambugu and Chaneyiwo (2008), which revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students when taught using mastery learning approach. This shows that both male and female students benefited equally when exposed to both mastery learning approach.

Conclusions

The study concludes that students taught mole concept using mastery learning approach was found effective in improving the academic performance compared to those taught mole concept using lecture method. Mastery learning approach is gender friendly since both genders showed improved academic performance when taught mole concept in chemistry

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and conclusion reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. Lecture method in this research study has been found to be less effective in improving the students' academic performance. Teachers should therefore explore mastery learning approach into the teaching and learning of various topics in chemistry so as to enhance students reflective thinking and thereby improving their general academic performance.
2. Mastery learning approach has been shown to improve academic performance for both sexes; therefore, Teachers should actively involve male and female students in learning activities to avoid gender stereotyping so as to help create equal educational opportunities for both male and female learners.
3. The Federal government through its ministries and agencies like the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) and the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) Gombe branch should provide adequate funds for training of science teachers in-form of seminars, workshops and conferences that focuses on Concept-mapping and mastery learning approaches and other activity-based teaching strategies that are more effective in promoting academic performance.
4. Mastery learning approach is a teaching method that requires more time for the development of learning objectives along with corresponding formative tests and corrective activities and since the usual allotted time in the school timetable is inadequate for the effective implementation of either mastery learning approach or concept-mapping strategy, curriculum developers and planners should therefore create more time on the school timetable for optimum result

References

- Adeyemo, S.A., & Babajide, F.T. (2014). Effects of mastery learning approach on students' achievement in Physics among secondary school students, Lagos state. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*,5(2),910-920.
- Bamidele, E. F., & Oloyede, E.O. (2013). Comparative effectiveness of hierarchical, flowchart and spider concept mapping strategies on students' performance in Chemistry. *World Journal of Education*, 3(11),66.
- Bamidele, E.F., Adetunji, A.A., Awodele, B. A., & Irinoye, J. (2013). Attitudes of Nigerian Secondary School Chemistry Students towards concept mapping strategies in learning the Mole Concept. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies, Sapienza University of Rome*,2(2),89-94.

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- Emendu, N.B. (2014). The role of Chemistry Education in National Development. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*, 3(3),12-17.
- Filgona, J., Filgona, J., & Sababa, L.K. (2017). Mastery Learning Strategy and Learning Retention: Effects on senior secondary School students' achievement in Physical Geography in Ganye Educational Zone, Nigeria. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 2(3), 1-14.
- Furo, K.V., & Eniayeju, P.A. (2014). The effect of concept mapping- guided discovery integrated teaching approach on Chemistry students' achievement and retention. *Educational Research and Review*, 9(22), 1218-1223.
- Mayanchi, L.M., Anya, C.A., & Kainuwa, A. (2017). Effects of mastery learning and problem-solving methods of teaching on Students' academic performance in Mathematics in Zamfara State. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 8(3),1-8.
- Meheux M.E. (2017). Effect of concept mapping teaching strategy on the academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics in Obio/Akpor Metropolis. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*,3(12),25-32.
- Sor, E.N., Jamabo, T.M., & Igwe, C. (2018). Effects of cooperative and concept mapping strategies on Students achievement in Chemistry in selected Secondary Schools, Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social & Science Education Research*, 6(3),11-20.
- Wambugu, P. W., & Changeiywo, J. M. (2008). Effects of mastery learning approach on secondary School Students' Physics achievement. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 4(3), 293-302.